

DETECTING AND CHARACTERIZING WATER ICE IN PERMANENTLY-SHADOWED LUNAR REGIONS USING A THREE-BAND LIDAR. E. A. Cloutis¹, A. Parkinson¹, D. M. Applin¹, and P. J. Mann¹, R. Kruzelecky², and the VMMO Science Team. ¹Department of Geography, University of Winnipeg, 515 Portage Avenue, Winnipeg, MB, Canada R3B 2E9. ²MPB Communications Inc.; e.cloutis@uwinnipeg.ca

Introduction: Lunar exploration is of interest because of the possibility of exploitable water ice deposits in permanently shadowed regions (PSRs) [1, 2]. They are also of scientific interest because past lunar exospheric conditions may be preserved in the ice [2].

Multiple previous studies have strongly suggested or confirmed that water ice could be present within PSRs [e.g., 3]. They can reach temperatures of <100 K, which is sufficient to allow for stable deposits over geological time scales. Detecting water ice within these PSRs could possibly be achieved through active reflectance spectroscopy [4].

The nature of surficial water ice in PSRs is a function of multiple factors. These include PSR temperature which relates to the long-term stability of water ice and can lead to complete sublimation and formation of a regolith lag deposit or complete sublimation, age of a PSR, and impact-generated regolith gardening which would dilute water ice with regolith [4]. Dust cover thickness, the percentage of ice covered by regolith, and regolith: ice ratio, and how dust and ice are mixed together could all influence the efficiency of detecting water ice [5].

We conducted laboratory experiments to test for how physical properties of ice + regolith affect our ability to detect water ice using a three-band lidar system (532, 1064, and 1560 nm), which has been proposed as an upcoming ESA-funded mission [6]. We consider how water ice: lunar material ratios, temperature, local slope, how the ice and regolith are physically arranged, as well as dust thickness all effect detectability and quantification.

Methodology: A lunar highland breccia meteorite, NWA 11444, was ground to produce an unsorted powder and subjected to a modified de-rusting process [7]. Reflectance spectroscopy and X-ray diffractometry were used to ensure that the de-rusting process was effective. The ice and NWA 11444 samples were frozen to -40° C. Selected samples were allowed to come to room temperature with continuous spectral collection to determine how long samples could be exposed to ambient conditions and remain frozen. Selected samples were also cooled in a liquid nitrogen bath for similar analysis.

Reflectance spectra (350-2500 nm) were acquired with an ASD Fieldspec Pro HR spectrometer. To simulate a lidar, we used a bifurcated fiber optic bundle, which provided co-aligned incidence and emission ($i=e=0^\circ$). To measure the effects of local slope on lidar

return, all samples except the pure powdered NWA 11444 were tilted 10°, 20°, 30° and 40° to normal, in addition to normal incidence. All spectra were measured relative to a calibrated Spectralon panel.

To create ice + regolith mixtures, powdered NWA 11444 was mixed with appropriate amounts of distilled water to produce various powder + water mixtures. The mixtures were placed into sample cups; these and a mortar and pestle were placed into a freezer overnight and cooled to -40° C. The next morning the samples were crushed within the freezer with the mortar and pestle to ensure the mixtures were homogeneous. The homogenized mixtures were packed into black sample cups and leveled with a glass slide. Once this process was complete the sample cups were returned to the freezer and left overnight to ensure the samples would be at -40° C when measured the next day.

Five ice + rock mixtures were made at 10 wt.% intervals, from 10 to 50 wt.% water ice. Reflectance values at 532 nm, 1064, and 1560 nm, and ratios of reflectance at these three wavelengths were assess which could be used to determine water ice lower detection limit and abundance.

Dust coverage was the final aspect of the experiment to determine the extent lunar regolith coverage affected water-ice detection. Three dust coverages of increasing thickness were used.

<u>Sample ID</u>	<u>Description</u>
NWA 11444 #1	90% Lunar sample 10% Distilled water, unsorted powder multiple incident angles
NWA 11444 #2	80% Lunar sample 20% Distilled water, unsorted powder multiple incident angles
NWA 11444 #3	70% Lunar sample 30% Distilled water, unsorted powder multiple incident angles
NWA 11444 #4	60% Lunar sample 40% Distilled water, unsorted powder multiple incident angles
NWA 11444 #5	50% Lunar sample 50% Distilled water, unsorted powder multiple incident angles
NWA 11444 #6	Loosely applied dust coating allowing a portion of ice to show, unsorted powder multiple incident angles
NWA 11444 #7	Loosely applied dust coating allowing no ice surface to show, unsorted powder multiple incident angles
NWA 11444 #8	Packed applied dust coating pressed down to ensure a flat surface, unsorted powder multiple incident angles
NWA 11444 #9	100 % unsorted powdered NWA 11444,

Figure 1. Percentage of NWA 11444 within ice mixture versus absolute reflectance at 532 nm. Shot at varying tilts.

Figure 2. Percentage of NWA 11444 within ice mixture versus 1530/532 reflectance ratio. Shot at varying tilts.

This study supplements previous studies conducted using lunar regolith simulants [8]. As mentioned, our analysis focused on 532, 1064 and 1560 nm absolute reflectance and reflectance ratios to determine water ice content.

Building on previous research [8], different phase angles were used to examine topographic effects on lidar return. These results were as expected, indicating that slope strongly influences absolute reflectance (Fig 1, 2). Reflectance at 532 nm was highest for the 40° slope measurements for a fixed water ice abundance with the smallest spread in values for 50 wt.% water ice. Increases in 532 nm reflectance as a function of water ice content were also greatest for the 40° tilt measurements (Fig. 1).

The 1530:532 nm ratio (Fig. 2) results are not as distinctive as the trends seen for 532 nm reflectance (Fig. 1). This demonstrates that reflectance ratios are less sensitive to local slopes than absolute reflectance.

The 50:50 sample spectra show the greatest difference as a function of tilt. This may be due to the sensitivity of reflectance to surface texture (Fig. 2). The other regolith+water ice mixtures show little difference as a function of tilt.

The final aspect of this experiment was as expected for regolith coverage influencing water ice spectra. As the thickness of the dust increases the detection of water ice decreases. Full coverage of ice by dust blocks detection of water ice (second and third dust coverages of NWA 11444 #7 and #8). However, if the dust cover is similar to that of NWA 11444 #6, with incomplete areal coverage by dust, then water ice is detectable. This data can be used to constrain minimum dust thicknesses in regions of no ice detection.

Conclusion: Ice detection is possible using reflectance spectroscopy at 532 and 1530 nm for water ice abundances of 10-50 wt.%. These results indicate that we can determine or constrain whether water ice is exposed at the lunar surface, or covered by a thin dust layer. Combining the observational data with models of ice formation and stability, we can better constrain whether water ice is present on the lunar surface, its abundance, and its areal extent. Absolute reflectance at 532 and 1530 nm, as well as 1530/532 nm reflectance ratios, provide some discrimination in this regard. Additionally, absolute reflectance combined with reflectance ratios may provide constraints on local slopes, which may be important for trafficability. In summary, regions within PSRs that are dust cover-free, or contain more than a few percent water ice can be detected.

Further studies: Further experiments are planned using lunar mare material as well as extending the study to different rock:water ice ratios, dust cover types, and examining the effects of regolith grain size.

References: [1] Nozette S. et al. (2001) *JGR*, 106, 23253–23266. [2] Kruzelecky R. V. et al. (2018) *ICES*, 227, 1–20. [3] Feldman W. C. et al. (2001) *JRG*, 106, 23231–23251. [4] Yoldi Z. et al. (2018) *LPS MMXIX*, Abstract # 2083. [5] Fisher E. A. et al. (2017) *Icarus* 292, 74–85. [6] Kruzelecky R. V. (20228) *SPIE* 12236, Abstract 122360A [7] Kiddell C. B. et al. (2017) *LPS XLVIII*, Abstract #2397.[8] Cloutis E. A. et al. (2018) *LPS XLIX*, Abstract #2083.

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